

The Attitude Regarding Social Interaction and Communication Problems among Children with Autism Spectrum Disorder

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Abstract

Autism spectrum disorder [ASD] is defined as a neurodevelopmental condition which is classically characterized by social interaction and communication difficulties with restrictive, repetitive behaviors and interests as the name suggests a spectrum of different presentations is possible ranging from severe disability all the way to cognitive strengths. Autism spectrum disorder [ASD] is a range of neurodevelopmental disorder that involves delays and the development of many basic skills and functions, including the ability to socialize and to communicate.

The samples required for the study was collected from children with autism, of Amara Soundarya Foundation, Special School, Bengaluru. The size of the sample was 65. random sampling method is used in the study.

Other findings highlight significant perceived barriers, such as inadequate training of teachers and limited access to specialized interventions. For instance, 43.1% agreed, and 23.1% strongly agreed that limited access to specialized interventions is a barrier. Furthermore, a notable 52.3% agreed, and 16.9% strongly agreed that children with ASD face social interaction barriers in their environment.

Overall, the results underline a strong consensus on the importance of structured interventions, peer interaction, and adequate support systems for enhancing social skills in children with ASD, alongside a recognition of systemic barriers in addressing these needs.

Introduction

Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is a neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by social communication deficits and repetitive sensory-motor behaviors with impairments in functioning often continuing into adulthood (Lord, et al., 2018). Its prevalence is on the rise and management of children with ASD entails a multidisciplinary approach. There is an increase from 1.8% to 7.1% of all diagnosed developmental disabilities over a period of 10 years [1]. Music has therapeutic potential [2] that can be put to use in children with neurodevelopmental disorders [3]. Music therapy has been used as an intervention for autism since the 1940s [4]. Music therapy research has explored its efficacy in multiple domains of functioning. A meta-analysis suggests medium to large effects of music therapy interventions for children with ASD [5]. [6] in their updated review of 26 studies (1,165 participants) reported that music therapy probably

reduces total autism symptom severity (SMD -0.83, 95% confidence interval -1.41 to -0.24; 9 studies, 575 participants; moderate-certainty evidence), enhances the global functioning and improves the quality of life. However, the team mentioned that there was no clear evidence of a difference in social interaction, nonverbal communication, and verbal communication immediately postintervention. Music and language have common neuroanatomical substrates viz. the Broca's region (inferior frontal gyrus) and temporoparietal regions (superior temporal gyrus, middle temporal gyrus and angular gyrus) [7]. There is limited research done in the Indian context. [8] compared the neurobehavioral outcomes of a music intervention to a nonmusical control intervention, in 51 children aged 6–12 years with autism who were randomized to receive 8–12 weeks of music (n = 26) or nonmusical intervention (n = 25) and reported improvement in social communication and

More Information

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postintervention functional brain connectivity. [9] conducted an intervention study in 52 children aged between 6 and 12 years recruited by convenience sampling and reported the therapeutic benefits of using music in enhancing social skills. Music is a universal language that is a feature of everyday life. It communicates emotions and has strong social connotations [10]. Exposure, peer and family influence, the activities one is engaged in while listening to music and one's internal preferences for structure, harmony, rhythm, timbre, or lyrics. India is known for its cultural diversity, which means that the musical preferences of Indian families may vary widely. Preferences of families will in turn determine a child's exposure. Moreover, children with autism may be sensitive to the affective aspects of music [11]. Hence, there is a dire need for scientific research in this area, so that the prevalent practices are aligned with evidence-based guidelines. The primary objective of this study is to explore the musical preferences of children with autism in India and the secondary objective is to assess current practices prevalent in their households and caregivers' attitude toward music therapy. It will help in assessing the feasibility of interventions using music and serve as a baseline to develop formal interventions in the future.

Materials and Method

The samples required for the study was collected from children with autism, of Amara Soundarya Foundation, Special School, Bengaluru. The size of the sample was 65. To collect the sample, random sampling method is used in the study. To carry out the evaluation and to see the relevance of the contents it has been given to the experts in the beginning. The structured questionnaire with the tool surveys and questionnaires to evaluate parents, teachers and caregivers of autistic children to assess the attitude regarding social interaction and communication problems among children with ASD. The study is conducted in a special school among autism children was attainable and achievable. It consists of 32 questions. Each of the responds carry 1-5 marks according to their answer [strongly agree-strongly disagree]. Frequency and percentage are calculated according to the responds to the sample.

Results and Discussion

This study provides a comprehensive look into the perceptions and experiences of parents, teachers, and caregivers concerning the social and communication challenges faced by children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD), along with the barriers and supports that exist within educational and social environments. Regarding age demographics, the highest percentage of respondents (26%) were aged 35-40, followed by 22% from ages 30-35. Female participants (56.9%) outnumbered males (43.1%), and most respondents were parents (58.5%), with teachers and caregivers comprising the rest.

Most participants believe that children with ASD struggle significantly with social interactions, as evidenced by 87.7% agreeing or strongly agreeing on this point. Additionally, there was strong consensus on the potential for improvement through structured interventions, with 81.5% endorsing the view that appropriate social interaction skills can be developed with targeted support. Similarly, 80% believe structured social activities benefit these children, and nearly 77% agree that non-verbal communication methods are effective in enhancing their communication.

Participants overwhelmingly recognize the importance of effective communication for children with ASD, with 77% noting it as one of the most challenging areas. Similarly, 77% acknowledge the importance of peer interactions for social development. The necessity of social skills training within the curriculum is broadly supported, as 70.8% believe it should be an essential part of educational planning. Regarding institutional support, respondents are divided; while 78.5% feel that adequate resources are provided for ASD children, there are concerns about barriers such as lack of teacher training and limited access to specialized interventions.

Barriers like bullying, lack of peer awareness, and inconsistent implementation of support strategies were seen as significant challenges, as most respondents (around 70%) agreed these are critical factors hindering social integration. Participants also noted a lack of individualized support plans as a barrier, with over 69% seeing this as a hindrance to effective intervention.

Overall, these results underscore the urgent need for comprehensive and accessible support systems for children with ASD, including teacher training, individualized planning, and structured social and communication programs. Respondents strongly support interventions that foster social and communication skills, as well as collaboration between schools, families, and specialists to ensure children with ASD receive the support necessary for improved social outcomes.

The study's participants were categorized by age, gender, and their relationship to children with autism spectrum disorder. Age distribution revealed that 20% of participants were aged 20-25, 17% were 25-30, 22% were 30-35, 26% were 35-40, and 15% were 40-45. Gender-wise, 43.1% were male, and 56.9% were female. Regarding their relationship to children with ASD, 58.5% were parents, 24.6% were teachers, and 16.9% were caregivers.

The responses to 29 questions assessed attitudes toward social interactions, communication, and perceived barriers in supporting children with ASD. Responses indicated a generally high level of

agreement on the challenges faced by children with ASD in social interactions and communication. For example, 50.8% strongly agreed that children with ASD struggle with social interactions, and 36.9% agreed. Many respondents (41.5% strongly agreed, 40% agreed) also felt that social interaction skills in children with ASD could improve with appropriate interventions.

The study also explored perceptions on structured social activities, peer interactions, and communication aids, with more than half of the respondents agreeing on their importance. For example, 52.3% strongly agreed that structured social activities benefit children with ASD. Most respondents (47.7% strongly agreed, 29.2% agreed) saw nonverbal communication methods as effective for children with ASD.

Other findings highlight significant perceived barriers, such as inadequate training of teachers and limited access to specialized interventions. For instance, 43.1% agreed, and 23.1% strongly agreed that limited access to specialized interventions is a barrier. Furthermore, a notable 52.3% agreed, and 16.9% strongly agreed that children with ASD face social interaction barriers in their environment.

Overall, the results underline a strong consensus on the importance of structured interventions, peer interaction, and adequate support systems for enhancing social skills in children with ASD, alongside a recognition of systemic barriers in addressing these needs.

The present study assesses the understanding and attitudes of teachers, parents, and caregivers regarding autism spectrum disorder in children, focusing on areas such as social interactions, intervention methods, communication challenges, and access to resources. Findings indicate both promising awareness and engagement as well as gaps in support and knowledge that need addressing.

Demographic Characteristics and Impact of Relationship with Children with ASD The demographic makeup of the sample includes parents (58.5%), teachers (24.6%), and caregivers (16.9%), a distribution reflecting different levels of interaction and influence on children's ASD support systems. Research shows that parents are often primary caregivers who shoulder significant responsibilities, including navigating therapeutic services and advocating for their children [9]. In this study, parents and caregivers together comprise the majority of respondents, suggesting that the insights reflect the first-hand struggles and experiences of those most closely engaged with ASD support systems.

Awareness and Knowledge of Social Interaction Challenges in ASD Respondents generally acknowledged the social interaction challenges that children with ASD face, with over 85% agreeing that

children with ASD struggle with social interactions. This aligns with prior research highlighting how children with ASD often experience difficulties in interpreting social cues and engaging in reciprocal communication [12]. The widespread agreement in this study suggests that awareness of these challenges is relatively high among the respondents, potentially due to direct observation or education. However, the need for improved training for caregivers and teachers was also highlighted, emphasizing a gap in effective professional support strategies [5].

Interventions and Support Strategies Most participants (81.5%) agreed that social skills can be improved through interventions. This perspective aligns with existing literature on the benefits of structured social skills training, such as peer-mediated intervention, which can significantly enhance social outcomes in children with ASD [2]. The findings suggest that the respondents recognize the potential for improvement, yet the moderate satisfaction levels with available resources hint at potential obstacles in accessing or implementing such interventions effectively. Previous studies suggest that barriers to accessing specialized services, including occupational and speech therapy, can hinder consistent and individualized support [4].

Nonverbal Communication and Technology Use The positive responses to the use of nonverbal communication tools and technology (76.9% and 81.5%, respectively) underscore a recognition of diverse communication needs in children with ASD. Research confirms that augmentative and alternative communication (AAC) tools, such as picture-based communication and tablet-based apps, can foster improved communication and reduce frustration. However, while respondents acknowledge these tools' efficacy, consistent implementation remains a challenge, particularly in environments where access to resources or training is limited.

School Environment and Resources The respondents' mixed responses on the adequacy of school resources highlight an ongoing challenge in educational support for children with ASD. Approximately 55.4% of respondents felt schools provided adequate resources, a sentiment that is echoed in literature critiquing the limitations of resource allocation in inclusive education settings. Additionally, many participants highlighted the necessity of teacher training, which is consistent with findings by [5], who emphasize that lack of ASD-specific training can limit teachers' abilities to foster an inclusive environment.

Barriers to Effective Support for Children with ASD The study identified several barriers, including limited awareness among peers, inconsistent implementation of support strategies, and lack of individualized support plans. These findings align with studies emphasizing that the social inclusion of children with ASD requires

more than just specialized programs—it demands a systemic shift in school culture and peer attitudes. Barriers like bullying and exclusion were also noted, consistent with previous research showing that children with ASD are often more vulnerable to bullying due to their social communication challenges.

The Role of Collaboration in ASD Support Nearly 67.7% of respondents agreed on the need for collaboration among parents, teachers, and therapists for effective intervention. This finding reflects studies on multidisciplinary approaches that stress the importance of integrated care for children with ASD. Collaborative efforts across caregivers and professionals are shown to enhance the effectiveness of interventions, ensuring a continuity of care that aligns with the child's evolving needs [2].

Conclusion

This study offers insights into the collective awareness, perceptions, and perceived barriers in supporting children with ASD. While there is significant awareness of the challenges and potential interventions, gaps remain in resources, training, and systemic support. The need for enhanced training, school resources, and a collaborative approach across care teams emerges as central to improving ASD support systems. Future research and policy efforts should focus on addressing these barriers to empower caregivers and educators with effective tools and training, ultimately fostering an inclusive and supportive environment for children.

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